

METHODOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH OF STUDENTS IN THE PRIMARY SCHOOL IN READING LESSONS

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Abstract.

The article discusses the methods of speech development in the lessons of reading primary school, oral and written speech, their interdependence, specific features, their speech development in the development of students' oral speech, the causes of shortcomings, ways to overcome them, and communication skills that need to be formed in students through achievement of speech development in the qualitative educational process.

Keywords.

speech, methodology, aspects of speech, life skills, human maturity, great scientists, spiritual heritage, Eastern education and upbringing, norms of the literary language, the art of thinking and oratory, the quality of education.

The granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language has created a great opportunity for the conduct of state affairs, education, training, and propaganda in our country in this language. The attitude towards the language has changed radically, studies of all its possibilities are being carried out on a large scale. However, it should also be remembered that it is a pity that speech culture, which is one of the factors determining the level of fulfillment of the social function of the language, has not developed sufficiently. Therefore, a deeper study of the field of speech culture is one of the most important issues. Therefore, elimination of defects and shortcomings in our speech, development of speech culture better than ever before is a political and social issue of national importance. It is appropriate that not only linguists, but representatives of all fields living in our republic pay attention to the work of dealing with this issue. Because speech culture is a component of universal human culture and determines people to be highly cultured. It is known that the main task of the subject of the mother tongue is to develop the student's speech in primary grades.

However, this task is also carried out within the framework of other educational subjects. In particular, there are many opportunities to develop

students' speech during reading lessons. That is, in the process of studying the texts in the textbook, elementary school students learn many words that are unfamiliar to them and their meaning, that is, their word wealth increases. It will be more appropriate if the teacher is not satisfied with explaining such words, but also creates phrases and sentences for the students with their participation. In this way, new words enter the active vocabulary of students. Cultivating speech includes both the history and theory of primary education pedagogy and the methodology of teaching culture of communication. First of all, a primary school teacher should understand the tasks of providing general aesthetic education to his students. These tasks should not be limited to teaching good manners. In this, the most important thing is to teach the child the culture of speech and to arouse interest in each activity, to create a need for speech activity with the help of words and sentences, as well as to acquire knowledge, skills and competencies in them. Speech has two forms - oral and written speech. Although these are interconnected, each has its own characteristics. In oral speech, sounds and words are pronounced through speech, and are received through the auditory organs. Therefore, in the development of oral speech of students, we must first identify the reasons for the shortcomings in their speech and find ways to eliminate it. A student who does not know how to speak beautifully, write well, write correctly, and express his thoughts fluently and clearly cannot master knowledge successfully. If the speech of every person is beautiful, perfect, pronunciation is clear and fluent, the scope of thinking is wide and the perception is deep.

Human beings express their inner feelings through speech, and speech is not fully developed or formed in the same way in all people. Some children not only mispronounce sounds, but cannot distinguish them from each other. Such defects in speech create significant difficulties for children in mastering lessons. In such cases, a speech therapist will need the help of training. It is known that the elimination of defects in the speech of elementary school students is the responsibility of students and speech therapists. It is necessary to check the child's speech and study the causes of speech disorders in order to identify pronunciation defects. For this purpose, each child fills out a speech check sheet and determines which sounds he pronounces correctly or incorrectly. Speaking - teaching to read, speak and write, to provide knowledge about the language that is suitable for the age and understanding of students, to increase their vocabulary, to develop attention and interest in the speech of others, aims to instill a love of reading. Dactyology (hand alphabet) is used in the early stages of teaching oral speech. This

thing serves only as an auxiliary tool as children learn and pronounce sounds. The leading place in all the activities conducted in primary school reading classes is the development of speech, which includes the tasks of teaching literacy, forming beautiful writing skills, and expanding the range of thinking.

In these lessons, it is necessary to aim for more practical goals, to form the skills of using language resources in speech, to think creatively, and to educate students' language sensitivity. Regularly developing their oral speech will provide practical help in creating coherent speech and text. It is known that there are different ways to perform these tasks. Giving a wide place to practical exercises in literacy classes and using interesting and lively things, technical tools, and various games and game-type exercises in instilling skills will give effective results. Stories, fairy tales, poems and proverbs related to the textbook are explained by reading or listening to unfamiliar words. Thus, in each lesson, regardless of what subject it is, our first task is to achieve conscious, fluent, correct and expressive reading of students, and to try to develop their speech. . It is known that speech is related to thinking, so it is cultivated in an integral connection with thinking. Logical principles such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalization are used in the lesson so that students can consciously understand the work read, understand its main content and idea. Various work methods are used in the analysis of the read work. Children tell the main participants in the story, create a schematic plan of the work under the guidance of the teacher (node, climax, solution). One of the means of developing students' speech in primary school reading lessons is a well-organized retelling. There are full, abbreviated, selective and creative retellings in the school experience. For elementary school students, it is easier to retell the text in full or close to the text, while other types are relatively more difficult. The teacher's question about the content of the story read in the retelling should make the students think about the details of the story, about the cause and effect of the connection between some events.

The persons participating in the development of the plot of the work, their behavior plays the main role. Children understand the content of the work better by analyzing the characters and their behavior. The teacher's question should be directed to tell about what the heroes of the work did, where and under what conditions their actions took place, to a consistent description of the events and to clarify the interrelationship. When the student tells the content of the read work with the help of the teacher's question, he uses not only analysis, but also synthesis: he connects (synthesizes) some facts, compares them, discusses them and draws a

conclusion. Often, elementary school students do not understand the content of the work as a result of not understanding the behavior of the participants, sometimes incorrectly or superficially. That is why the teacher should formulate the question very carefully, it will make the child think, think, discuss the behavior of the participating persons, the connection of events, help to compare them with each other, and determine their positive and negative aspects. should be. The more accurately the reader can describe the behavior of the participants in the work, the more he will understand the main content of the story, the more he will retell it independently. Consistent retelling of the content of the read work helps to plan it. In planning, the reader divides the story into parts and identifies the main idea in each part.

All this is analytical work. Then they move on to synthetic work, that is, children find titles for parts of the story. In the process of making a plan under the guidance of the teacher, the students think about what the primary and secondary issues are in each part of the read story, and how to express the idea briefly and clearly. Working on finding a title, discussing the title found by the students as a team, and the process of making a plan itself should activate the child's thinking ability, inculcate the habit of proving and justifying his reasoning. If the plan made in the process of reading and analyzing the work is written on the board, it will help to retell the content of the story consistently. The task of telling a story based on a plan is to master the content in a given sequence. Retelling on the basis of a plan is an independent form of telling the content of the work in relation to teacher questioning. The next stage in mastering the content of the read work is short story telling. For abbreviated narration, works that are divided into 2-3 parts, these parts are clearly distinguished, and the content is simple, are chosen. Teaching short story telling is organized as follows: the teacher reads the first predetermined part of the story, and together with the students, the most important, main idea is determined. In this, students sometimes use words from the work. If this is difficult for students, they can tell the main idea of the section in their own words. Then the students decide with the teacher what not to talk about in the short story of this part, which are secondary or less important points.

The same work is done with other parts of the work, and the students retell the work in abbreviated form. It is taught from the 3rd grade to summarize the read work. Selective storytelling is one of the means of developing children's thinking and speech. In selective narration, the reader: 1) consciously separates a part of the read text, its limits; 2) tells only one event from the story; 3) tells the content of the

story only in one plot direction. Methodical methods that are widely used in primary grade explanatory reading classes help children to develop the skill of selective retelling: 1) telling a story based on a picture drawn in the story; 2) telling a story based on a picture depicting an event in the story; 3) answering questions that require selective retelling. The student analyzes the read text when he is prepared to tell a selective story. Such an analysis develops children's thinking, independence in their speech and helps to master the content of the read text. Creative activities related to reading the story also develop students' speech and thinking. These are: 1) creative retelling; 2) staging; 3) draw a picture of the read work; continuing the story.

1. In creative retelling, the story is told by changing the conditions or form of the read story, or the story is told by filling it with new episodes.

2. In staging or dramatization, students change the read story into a scene. To do this, they think about the script for the story, the costume, the gestures of the participants, turn the monologic speech into a dialogic speech (this is the most important task from the point of view of teaching the language).

3. When drawing a picture for the read story, the student chooses a picture from the pictures drawn by artists that matches the content of the read work or draws a picture himself. If the student cannot draw a picture well, he orally describes the picture he wants to draw, that is, he draws a picture with words.

4. The method of continuing the read story is widely used in school experience. This method is used in works where the content of the story allows it to continue.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in speech development training, children's reading and telling stories is especially important. Teaching the retelling of works of art and staging them, memorizing the poem imposes a great skill and responsibility on the teacher. The more vividly the content of the work of art is expressed by the author, the more expressive and meaningful the speeches of the participants are, the more it excites children, the development of their feelings, the long memory of the events that happen to the heroes of the work, the vocabulary has a positive effect on the enrichment and grammatically correct formation of speech. Children can easily answer the teacher's questions about the work, repeat some words and sentences, characterize the positive and negative sides of the characters, imitate the teacher and try to imitate their voice.

The development, prospects, well-being, spiritual growth of every country, becoming one of the most developed countries in the world depends on young

people who are educated, have high intellectual potential, who embody good qualities in their hearts and minds, and are mature and perfect in all respects, the destiny of the Motherland. To bring up a devoted, faithful generation, to raise the quality and content of education to the highest levels, first of all, it is an honorable and at the same time responsible task for teachers and educators. The historically formed content of human experience is summarized in verbal form, and its description and mastering implies the participation of speech in this process. Speech opens the way for a child to all the achievements of human culture. In general, the formation of personality and all basic mental processes (reception, thinking, etc.) is also related to the development of speech in a child. The special place of speech in the mental formation of a child makes it very important to know the conditions and factors that support its development at different stages.

With the development of speech, the issue of moving forces becomes important due to the fact that it occurs in the form of rapid jumps. Searching for the optimal form of organization of methods that allow to ensure the high level of intellectual and speech development of students, the formation of their language skills in primary school reading lessons, and to solve issues about the content and forms of such education in theoretical and practical research. new methodological recommendations are being developed. Effective use of the given opportunities, ensuring the effectiveness of the quality of the provided education requires great pedagogical skills, high competence and creativity from a modern teacher.

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